

Formation of Nitron from the Reaction Between α -Nitrostyrene and *o*-Methylstyrene

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Manuscript received 6 September 1991, revised 6 December 1991, accepted 22 January 1992

2-Phenyl-5-(2-methylphenyl)-1 pyrrolin-1 oxide is obtained by the cycloaddition of α nitrostyrene and *o*-methylstyrene. The structure of the compound has been established on the basis of pmr, cmr and mass spectral studies.

It has been reported that nitrosoalkenes are generated as intermediates in the reactions of α -halo-oximes with bases^{1,2}. The involvement of the nitrosoalkene as a diene and its [4+2]cycloaddition with dienophiles was first reported by Faragher and Gilchrist³. The products are generally 5,6-dihydro-4*H*-1,2-oxazines.

Several alkenes were used for the cycloaddition with α -nitrostyrene (generated *in situ* by the treatment of α -haloacetophenone oxime with base) to construct the heterocyclic system (1)⁴. As a part of our ongoing project dealing with the construction and ring cleavage of the 1,2-oxazine system (1), we

employed the olefin *o*-methylstyrene for the cycloaddition with α -nitrostyrene. We expected the formation of 3-phenyl-6-(2-methylphenyl)-5,6-dihydro-4*H*-1,2-oxazine (2). But we obtained a new nitron (3), viz. 2-phenyl-5-(2-methylphenyl)pyrroline.

Evidence⁴ is available for similar nitron formation in the case of the reaction of 2-methoxypropene and α -nitrostyrene. But in this case the nitron (4) is formed as a minor product along with the expected oxazine (5) which formed as the major product. It has been suggested that the transoid form of the α -nitrostyrene led to the formation of the nitron (Scheme 1).

The formation of the nitron (3) was confirmed by its spectral data : pmr δ 1.63 (3H, CH₃ at C-2'), 2.14 (2H, CH₂ at C-4), 2.54 (2H, CH₂ at C-3), 7.23–7.63 (11H, ArH and benzylic proton at C-5); cmr δ 20.2 (CH₃ at C-2'), 29.1 (C-4), 29.5 (C-3), 78.1 (C-5), 135.9 (C-2).

If the expected oxazine (2) is formed then there should be a doublet of a doublet in the pmr spectrum of the compound at δ 4.0–5.0. Since this characteristic signal is not found, it is concluded that the

compound formed is the nitrone (3). The signal for the benzylic proton (C_5-H) is not recognisable. However, we have assumed after calculating the integration that the signal for the benzylic proton is merged with the aromatic signal. This benzylic proton is very much deshielded since it is adjacent to a positive centre. So, on the basis of the literature evidence⁴ we conclude that the nitrone (3) is formed as a result of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of the nitro-styrene to *o*-methylstyrene.

The mass spectrum is also in agreement with the proposed structure (3). The parent ion has a m/z value of 251 (agrees with the expected formula weight). The probable mass fragmentation pattern is shown in Scheme 2.

Experimental

Melting point is uncorrected. Silica gel (60–100 mesh) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for tlc. Pmr and cmr spectra were recorded on a Varian XL-300 spectrometer in $CDCl_3$ using TMS as the internal standard and the mass spectrum on a Jeol-DX 300 instrument operating at 70 eV. CH_2Cl_2 was distilled and dried over molecular sieves of 4Å.

The cycloaddition was carried out by stirring a solution of *o*-bromoacetophenone oxime (2 mmol) and *o*-methylstyrene (20 mmol) in dry dichloromethane in the presence of anhydrous sodium carbonate (11 mmol) following the literature procedure⁴. The solvent was flash-evaporated after overnight stirring. The residue was subjected to column chromatography (eluent $CHCl_3$ -EtOAc, 19 : 1) and the compound isolated was recrystallised from ethanol as white powder, m.p. 120–24°d.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank the D.S.T., New Delhi, for funding this project. They also wish to thank Prof. R. W. Murray, University of Missouri, St. Louis, U.S.A. for recording pmr and cmr spectra and Prof. N. Venkatasubramanian, Director, INBRI, Bangalore for the mass spectra.

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